

Dataset Report

2019-01-15 Avalanche, Wildi-Rüchi-Chaiserren, Brämabühl

event and data description

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1 Description of meteo conditions and avalanches

The avalanche event at Brämabühl in Davos, Switzerland took place on 15 January 2019. Three avalanches were artificially triggered and reached the road during the avalanche cycle around 10:00 o'clock in the morning.

The day before the event, the avalanche bulletin had issued a high danger warning (level 4) (see Figure 1), recommending avalanche experts to focus on transportation routes. A prolonged snow storm had persisted for several days, preventing local avalanche experts from cleaning the avalanche tracks. They were facing roughly 60 cm of new snow and wind-drifted accumulations deposited on soft, potentially erodible layers. These conditions needed careful consideration, as the substantial amount of snow could potentially be eroded, significantly increasing the volume of any subsequent avalanche.

Data availability

All three avalanches were artificially triggered from a helicopter as part of a controlled release operation. The development and extent of the powder clouds were documented through photographs taken during the event (for Rüchitobel and Chaiserren). One day after the avalanche occurrence, snow height were measured using drone-based photogrammetry.

1.1 DTM

A 1x1m digital terrain model in coordinate system EPSG:2056 - CH1903+ / LV95.

File name: Braemabuehl_DTM_1m.tif

1.2 Snowheight after the event

Calculated difference of the digital terrain model one day after the event and the summer digital terrain model from swisstopo results in the snowheight with a resolution of 10 cm.

File name: Braemabuehl_HS_20190116_10cm.tif

1.3 Forest

The orthophoto was used to draw the outline of the forest area at Brämabühl.

File name: Braemabuehl_Forest.shp

1.4 Release polygones

The release areas were identified from the orthophoto. The Stauchwall is clearly visible in the drone data. Wildi and Rüchi each have only one release area, while Chaiseren is split into two areas that are stored in a single release file.

File name: Chaiseren_RelArea_all.shp, Rüchi_RelArea.shp, Wildi_RelArea.shp

1.5 Deposition outline

The deposition outlines were identified from the orthophoto.

File name: Chaiseren_DepoArea_all.shp, Rüchi_DepoArea.shp, Wildi_DepoArea.shp

1.6 Powder cloud outline

Rough estimation of outlines of the powder clouds were identified from the orthophoto.

File name: Chaiseren_PowArea_all.shp, Rüchi_PowArea.shp, Wildi_PowArea.shp

1.7 Pictures of powder cloud

After the Wildi avalanche was triggered and the blasting expert observed how far it traveled, he started to take pictures while Rüchi and Chaiseren came down. As a result, several images capture the evolution of the powder cloud. Using the timestamps on the pictures, the velocity of the powder can be roughly estimated.

1.8 Snowpits

at close meteo stations at roughly altitude of releases at Weissfluhjoch stations (WFJ2) and in the valley Stilli (SLF2). Release density.

Figure 1: (a) Meteorological measurements of air temperature TA, snow surface temperature TSS, total snow height HS, wind direction DW and wind speed VW at Weissfluhjoch (WFJ2) and Davos (SLF2) during the snow storm period before the avalanche got triggered. The trigger time of the avalanche is marked by the grey vertical bar (Data Source: IMIS). (b) Avalanche Bulletin from 14 January 2019, 8 AM showing danger level 4 in the Dischma valley on all aspects from 1800 m a.s.l. and higher. Note that the Dischma Valley is very close to regions with avalanche level 5 (Data Source: SLF). (c) Resulting SNOWPACK simulations based on the weather station measurements at SLF2 and WFJ2 at 3 AM in the morning.